

1 **CCL18 in irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total gene expression by RNA-sequencing in humans with irritable bowel syndrome to
7 identify defining molecular features in IBS. We describe here specific loss of the chemokine *CCL18* in
8 humans with irritable bowel syndrome diarrhea-type, or IBS-D.

9 Citations

10 1. Islam, S.A., Ling, M.F., Leung, J., Shreffler, W.G. and Luster, A.D., 2013. Identification of human
11 CCR8 as a CCL18 receptor. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 210(10), pp.1889-1898.

12 2. Vulcano, M., Struyf, S., Scapini, P., Cassatella, M., Bernasconi, S., Bonecchi, R., Calleri, A.,
13 Penna, G., Adorini, L., Luini, W. and Mantovani, A., 2003. Unique regulation of CCL18 production by
14 maturing dendritic cells. *The Journal of Immunology*, 170(7), pp.3843-3849.

15 3. Chenivesse, C., Chang, Y., Azzaoui, I., Ait Yahia, S., Morales, O., Plé, C., Foussat, A., Tonnel,
16 A.B., Delhem, N., Yssel, H. and Vorng, H., 2012. Pulmonary CCL18 recruits human regulatory T cells. *The*
17 *Journal of Immunology*, 189(1), pp.128-137.

18 GSE146853